

Fragments II & Another Manichaean Harmony
by Brian Paul Kaess

1. 'You and the Divine are One. Gnosticism teaches that there is a divine light or spirit in each one of us. Salvation arises from the knowledge that there is no difference between God and Man, between the spark of light in man and the Land of Light or God of Heaven¹. One must have spiritual knowledge. The light of the soul must be freed from the body as it ascends to heaven. Salvation does not come from faith or acts, as in later Christianity. The Divine dwells in each one of us. Gnostics believe that Jesus taught secret, esoteric, mysterious teachings only available to the learned few. But one must remember that the Papyrus or Papyri that the Gnostics wrote on and buried in the sand was no Internet. So to say today that knowledge is only available to a learned few would be like denying the existence of the Internet. Basically, Gnosticism is 'a people are better than their surroundings' or 'we're better than this people!' Philosophy.'
2. 'Where the Right & Left meet is in Genealogy.'
3. 'Do the job for America!' – Coach Daiyantis
4. 'Judas was the Handmaiden of Satan...'
5. 'Let me be the Joseph Smith of Manichaeism.'
6. 'The Confederacy's numbers were known to swell whenever the Union attacked the Shenandoah. Just think of it as rebels overrunning hills looking for Yankees.'
7. 'It is true that Lee surrendered (April 9, 1865) at the McLean House in Appomattox Court House, Virginia, but also true that Confederate President Jefferson Davis urged the South to fight on (April 2, 1865) with his last proclamation at Danville, Virginia, until his capture on May 10th, 1865. So we see that cooler heads prevailed.'
8. 'It is well that we have illustrated that which is best.'

So for you there are no more enemies and rivals, but yours is the eternal victory.² Show mercy upon us. Uncover your bright figure, you who are the loveliest of all sights. Let us greet the Sovereign of Paradise. May the demons become ashamed and the Light freed from the Darkness. For the sake of the Kindred O' Mani are you called the mercy of the world. Therefore go to the heaven of Light, where the gods dwell and are forever at peace. There they receive the original splendor in the radiant palace. Don the resplendent garment and live forever in Paradise. Let us rise to the radiant light of the East, the morning dawn has come. Praise the Righteous God who keeps guard in peace and joy. Be blessed O Righteous One when you reach the twelve gates of heaven. Splendid is your form and it blazes up. The sons of Darkness are conquered by the sons of Day, thus awakened, while both heaven and earth convulse. A treasure of jewels has become your salvation. We hold up the diadem, banner and white sign to the Compassionate Lord. Let the assembly of the apostles gather. We read from the book of the free souls. Let us be Joyful in the New Paradise.

¹ See *The Gospel of Judas* from the *Codex Tchacos*, Edited by Rodolphe Kasser, Marvin Meyer, and Gregor Wurst. New York. 2006. The Introduction has an excellent explanation of Gnosticism.

² See *The Manichaean Hymn Cycles in Parthian* by Mary Boyce. New York. 1964.

So blessed are the shepherd & the judge who lead us to the eternal dominion. To the brave chieftains do we pay homage. At the eternal realm lead me to my family. Lead me up the road that is the secret, that gate of salvation. Fulfil, oh God, your will in me! Pleasure and lust are like food mixed with poison. Hold back your soul from their trap! Through blind habits one may perish. Do not fall into eternal bondage. Lead my soul to the Eternal Paradise! So to Your Light will I give praise, Lovely apparition, O' Spring of Life. Let the Living Spirit gather pearls. We sail upon noble ships, the spiritual vessels called Good Faith. Let our heart be filled with joy at this miraculous power. You Mani with that sweet name who embrace the just and friendly God. You are the brilliance and the splendor of the seven climes of the world. Let the wise helmsman pass on. The emanations are signs and aspects-living, wakeful & eternal. The Light is come. Arise, brethren, give praise.

Let us praise of the World of Light. Mar Ammo was the name of Mani's great apostle to the Parthians. He was the author of the Hymn Cycles. It Contains seventy-eight Odes, each of which is in four lines. So let him be praised. We begin with the soul in distress. Fire and Fog daunt it as well as hideous demons. Life ebbs from its body and it asks in despair 'Who shall save me? The Savior comes with loving words and the demons slink away. The soul is promised salvation on this 'day of death.' The soul is clothed in a Garment of Light and thereafter rescued from all sins. The Savior brings comfort and a promise of redemption. This reminds one of Jesus on the Cross, crying out, 'Lord, O Lord, why hast thou abandoned me.' In Manichaeism, the soul, freed from the body, must await its fate after death. Herein the living may address the dead. The soul has left the body, that abode of Darkness that is full of fear. The soul must bear up beneath the alarm of death. It is the hour of 'going up from the body.' Its foes are a merciless crowd not unlike vultures. Uttering praises to its redeemer, it receives the Victory and ascends to Paradise. The ascent of the soul after death held a place of paramount importance in the older gnostic religions, and Manichaeism is little different. Manichaeism was the fruit of the gnostics!

Virtue, as was taught by Mani, depended on an understanding of the principles of Light and Darkness. Good actions, not words, secured a passage heavenwards for the soul. The ascent became not an ordeal, but a triumph. Let the watchposts of the hostile planets lean to heaven. Thy defense is Christ who will receive thee into his Kingdom. I bear a burden which is not my own. I am in the midst of my enemies, like sheep that have no shepherd. I am the Light that shines forth, that gives joy to souls. The First Man (king of the New Paradise) is my father whose will I have carried out. Let us sacrifice our selfish desires to the Altar of Light. Lo, the Darkness I have subdued as the Sphere turns around the Sun. Go aboard the Ships of Light and receive thy garland. Glory and honour to our Lord Mani and his holy Elect and the soul of the blessed Mary.

The New Paradise appears to have the same relation to the Real Paradise as Purgatory does to Hell, in Christian cosmology, except in opposite directions! It is a preliminary stage of Heaven, a temporary, intermediate realm of salvation for the righteous. It is a veritable, staging ground toward heaven or the Real Paradise. The Hymns may have consisted of twelve cantos, one for each hour of the day of celebration. Let us enjoy the sweetness of eternal life. I reverence you, O God; forgive my sins, save my soul, lead it up to the New Paradise!

We must know and accept thy teachings, Beneficent Sovereign- show mercy to us. The Envoy of the Father heals spirits, gives joy, and removes sorrows. He is a place, limitless, where Darkness never comes. All the monasteries and their dwelling places are magnificent, for they are happy in the Light and know no pain. All who enter there stay for eternity. Their clothes are forever clean and bright. Their verdant garlands never fade and are wreathed brightly in numberless colours. There is no fear or terror, for in those lands destruction does not exist. Ascend up to the knowledge, lauded and magnificent. The depth of their dominion has no boundary. For here there are no dark shadows. Here fear is unknown. Happiness and esteem remain unbroken. All is radiant and will never wither. Let our spirits remain high as we ascend! For the monasteries are all splendid, full of light.

Save me from the jaws of the beasts who are full of terror and without pity. Lead me over the walls and across the moats. It is Mani who will lead us beyond rebirths to the sacred abode. Let the Dark Powers perish in agony and perdition in that place where there is no mercy. Save me and take me beyond this world. So I wept for my soul.

We have left the dark valley and all harshness. There all is anguish and the stab of death. No golden drop of water is ever found there. Do not tumble and fall into that bitter hell. For now we have reached eternity. It is well that we have passed beyond. Here it is not all the idols, altars and images that save. Let us pass the boundary and let my heart be taken away. We are striving ever higher and higher. There the fragrant garlands are sacred and immortal. Praise those with living blessings. We have finished the End of this fragment of the fifth canto.

Let me hear the voice of the beneficent king. Beware of the watch-post of the enemy and the swirling pool of Hell. Beware of the desert where there is no water. May the prince guard thee with tranquility. I shall make thee free from all the Dark Powers. I shall soar up with wings high over the walls. You shall wear on thy head the diadem of sovereignty. Depth was gained in the victory and the brilliant jewel obtained. We have reached the fortress, high and vast, of the noble Emperor of the Sogdian Rock³. For the pious we clothe in praise. Let us wear the rich garment of gladness.

The Third Messenger is the Savior of my Soul. Thou shalt not fall into Hell, but rather shall pass the border and receive the diadem of felicity. And even as I had strictly believed and been patient in righteousness, so he gave me the Victory above all the Dark Powers. Let us reign in gladness and freedom and abide in tranquility. Rich Friend of the beings of Light! In mercy grant me strength and succour me with every gift! Array my soul, O Lord! Thou art the Friend, praised and beneficent!

Pain was heaped on pain. Fire was kindled, and the fog was full of smoke. All the demons transfixed me with fear. Their fury gathered, amid an ocean of flame. Let me not be tossed and troubled as a sea with waves. Turmoil most violent raged. Amid the banked clouds of rain, I was lifted on the crest of a wave and thereby hidden. Fear gripped those on board. Anguish reached me on all sides⁴. There was terror and wreck before the break of day. My soul weeps within.

All the comets (?) quivered, and the stars were whirled about, and each of the planets turned awry its course. The earth shook, my foundation beneath, and the height of the heavens sank down above. All of the rivers dried up at their source. Harm befell the course of the zodiac's wheel.

³ A John Keats-style interpolation hearkening back to Alexander.

⁴ Similar to the Book of Job.

The brethren weep amid their stature of might in a hell without pity or compassion. Who shall save me at the hour of death? Who shall save me from the blazing fire of my own agony? Let not your prison be anger. Lead me to that land without tremors, where there is beauty never ending. I beheld the Saviour as he shone before me. I lifted up my eyes and saw that death was hidden by the Envoy (i.e. Jesus).

Thou art the buried treasure, the chief of my wealth, the pearl which is the beauty of all the gods. I am the righteousness sown in thy limbs, and (in) the stature of (thy) soul. Thou art my Beloved, the Heroic Mind. Through thee a diadem was bound on all (our) foes during the hours of tyranny. For thy sake was there battle and tremor in all the heavens and the bridges of the earths. And thereafter sped all the (Dark) Powers. For thy sake shone forth the Apostles who reveal the Light above, and uncover the root of Darkness. Thou art the exalted Trophy, the sign of Light that puts Darkness to flight. I have come to save thee from the sinner and bring gladness to thy Heart. I shall set open before thee the gates in all the heavens, and in this lofty kingdom, you shall no longer be vexed. I shall lead you to your home, the blessed abode⁵. I shall show to thee the Mother of the beings of Light. They rejoice and are lauded in happiness. For ever shalt thou [dwell] joyful among them all, beside all the Jewels and the venerable Gods. Fear and death shall never overtake (thee more), nor ravage, distress and wretchedness. Rest shall be thine in this place of salvation.

Come, spirit, fear no more! Death has fallen, and sickness fled away. The term of troubled days is ended, its terror departed amid clouds of fire. Come, spirit, step forth! Let there be no desire for the house of affliction. Truly thou wast cast out from thy native abode. Come yet nearer, in gladness without regret.

The body falls and melts as snow in sunshine. There is no abiding for any fair form. It withers and fades as a broken rose, that wilts in the sun, whose grace is destroyed. Yet come, thou spirit, and be not fond of the sum of hours and the fleeting days⁶. Turn not back. Yet, Desire is death, and leads to destruction. Remember, O spirit! Look on the anguish thy ravages have born. Regard the world and the prison of creation; for all desires will be swiftly destroyed. All the heavens will fall down into the deep. The trap of destruction will swiftly close upon those deceivers who brag therein⁷. The whole of the lusts, gilded with all (their) charm,... fire, will be heaped upon perdition. Each mansion will be broken open. Who will escape the injury of Heaven?

Thou art my word, and my panoply of war which saved me from all sinners. When trembling and affliction overwhelms the Soul, do not fear, I shall crush and slay all the demons, and release you from the dungeon. And then I shall bear thee afar with all thy wounds. I shall release thee from all anguish and ravages. We shall pass through Perfect Light.

They will fall into the deep and be devoured in death. They will clothe themselves in darkness, distress, and fire. None will open for them the gate of hell. Deception will be laid bare... they will receive (their) reward. Be glad of heart on this day of departing. My soul is saved from all the sins which day by day oppressed me ever in anguish. I am clothed with a garment of Light. I am arrayed and succoured by the Saviour of my spirit. Thou wast suspended amid all rebirths. Truly for Thee Satan was a deceptive partner. But do not worry. Thou wast held back from the abyss.

⁵ The blessed abode is the place where you want to be in Manichaeism.

⁶ Similar to Ecclesiastes 1:2–11.

⁷ The tone is similar to the Book of Psalms.

In the blessed abode shone forth Light, elating and lovely and full of gladness, pervading all my mind. In joy unbounded he spoke with me, raising up my soul from deep affliction. To me he sayeth, Come, spirit! fear not. I am thy glad tidings of hope. And Jesus said: I am thy Light, radiant, primeval, thy Great Mind and complete Hope of the World.